

Smarandache's Quantum Chromodynamics Formula:

In order to save the colorless combinations prevailed in the Theory of Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) of quarks and antiquarks in their combinations when binding, we devise the following formula:

$$\mathbf{Q - A \in \pm M3} \quad (1)$$

where $M3$ means multiple of three,

i.e. $\pm M3 = \{3 \cdot k \mid k \in \mathbb{Z}\} = \{\dots, -12, -9, -6, -3, 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, \dots\}$,

and Q = number of quarks, A = number of antiquarks.

But (1) is equivalent to:

$$\mathbf{Q \equiv A \pmod{3}} \quad (2)$$

(Q is congruent to A modulo 3).

To justify this formula we mention that 3 quarks form a colorless combination, and any multiple of three ($M3$) combination of quarks too, i.e. 6, 9, 12, etc. quarks. In a similar way, 3 antiquarks form a colorless combination, and any multiple of three ($M3$) combination of antiquarks too, i.e. 6, 9, 12, etc. antiquarks. Hence, when we have hybrid combinations of quarks and antiquarks, a quark and an antiquark will annihilate their colors and, therefore, what's left should be a multiple of three number of quarks (in the case when the number of quarks is bigger, and the difference in the formula is positive), or a multiple of three number of antiquarks (in the case when the number of antiquarks is bigger, and the difference in the formula is negative).

Quark-Antiquark Combinations.

Let's note by q = quark $\in \{\text{Up, Down, Top, Bottom, Strange, Charm}\}$,

and by a = antiquark $\in \{\text{Up}^\wedge, \text{Down}^\wedge, \text{Top}^\wedge, \text{Bottom}^\wedge, \text{Strange}^\wedge, \text{Charm}^\wedge\}$.

Hence, for combinations of n quarks and antiquarks, $n \geq 2$, prevailing the colorless, we have the following possibilities:

- if $n = 2$, we have: qa (biquark – for example the mesons and antimessons);
 - if $n = 3$, we have qqq , aaa (triquark – for example the baryons and antibaryons);
 - if $n = 4$, we have $qqaa$ (tetraquark);
 - if $n = 5$, we have $qqqqa$, $aaaaq$ (pentaquark);
 - if $n = 6$, we have $qqqaaa$, $qqqqq$, $aaaaaa$ (hexaquark);
 - if $n = 7$, we have $qqqqqaa$, $qqaaaaa$ (septiquark);
 - if $n = 8$, we have $qqqqaaaa$, $qqqqqaa$, $qqaaaaaaa$ (octoquark);
 - if $n = 9$, we have $qqqqqqqq$, $qqqqqqaaa$, $qqaaaaaaa$, $aaaaaaaaa$ (nonaquark);
 - if $n = 10$, we have $qqqqqaaaaa$, $qqqqqqqaa$, $qqaaaaaaa$ (decaquark);
- etc.